

THE RULE OF LAW UNDER SCRUTINY: DISCRETIONARY POWERS AS A NORMATIVE FACTOR OF CORRUPTION IN THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

Nataša Pelivanova

Faculty of Security - Skopje
natasa.pelivanova@uklo.edu.mk

Mirjana Ristovska

Faculty of Law, UKLO
mirjana.ristovska@uklo.edu.mk

Abstract

This paper undertakes a normative analysis of the rule of law principle in the Republic of North Macedonia focusing on the critical examination of discretionary powers and their potential role in facilitating systematic corruption. The main focus will be on the regulatory framework governing discretionary powers to identify legal gaps and institutional weaknesses that could be a potential source of corrupt practices.

Methodologically, the paper employs normative analyses, comparative analyses, empirical method and case studies, with a primary emphasis on European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) judgments.

Additionally, the paper proposes measures to constrain discretionary powers and enhance mechanisms for combating systematic corruption in our country.

Keywords: rule of law, corruption, discretionary powers.

1. INTRODUCTION

The importance of good governance and raising awareness among citizens to demand high professional standards, efficient institutions and successful public administration, as well as greater accountability, is one of the factors for a successful fight against corruption – particularly in situations where discretionary decisions are involved.¹

¹ Discretion (Latin *discretio*, French *diskretion*) is prudence and caution in speech and behavior, attention, restraint; taking into account the sensitivities of others; restraint, silence; discretion, generosity or attention (towards the winner). This term also has additional meanings: to surrender to discretion - to surrender to the mercy and grace of others; discretion, - according to one's own will; discretionary right (law) - the right to make decisions within the legal framework at one's own discretion, against which there is no legal remedy.

Discretionary authority (Latin *discretio*, in contrast, from Latin *discernere* – to distinguish) is a form of weaker legal binding of a state body to a legal norm. The subject of discretionary authority, although less frequently, can also be issues of procedural law in administrative and judicial (civil)

The establishment of a framework for systemic limitation of discretionary powers enables the strengthening of legal certainty for citizens and protection from the arbitrariness of institutions, but also encourages reform in strengthening the control mechanisms for the exercise of these powers by institutions. Discretionary powers, in the simplest terms, represent an opportunity for public sector institutions to freely decide in certain situations. Such powers are held by institutions belonging to all three branches of government (legislative, executive and judicial).²

Discretionary powers are an institute of public law that refer to the ability of public sector institutions to freely decide for the more efficient and effective achievement of certain goals. Discretionary powers of the administration mean freedom in consideration, action and decision-making, which means the ability to choose a solution, to do something or not, and if the option to do something is chosen, to choose one of the possible ways (Breban, 2002, p. 204).

Discretionary powers are not unlimited (Breban, 2002).³ Institutions vested with such authority are required to consider the purpose for which the law confers it, and their decisions must be thoroughly justified and clearly explained.

However, these powers are not resistant to abuse and in the absence of a clear procedure and guidelines for their application and control, they can serve as an instrument for materializing corruption, cronyism and clientelism (employment in the public sector, appointment of management and leadership structures in public sector institutions, allocation of public resources/funds, citizens' access to public services and making certain political decisions.) (Guidelines for the exercise of discretionary powers, p. 5).

So, as Munir, Khan, and Ahmad (2020, p. 183-191) emphasize, certain standards have to be laid down by the legislature, administration and norms of practice to maximize the advantages of discretionary powers and to minimize the susceptibility of their exploitation.

In accordance with Recommendation No. R (80)2 of the CoE Committee of Ministers, an administrative authority, when exercising a discretionary power: 1. does not pursue a purpose other than that for which the power has been conferred; 2. observes objectivity and impartiality, taking into account only the factors relevant to the particular

proceedings, and very rarely in criminal proceedings. It is most often applied in administrative proceedings in the form of discretionary (free) assessment (French: *pouvoir discrétionnaire*: discretionary authority, German: *freies Ermessen*: free assessment), which means the authority of the competent body to choose, between two or more possibilities provided for in the legal norm, that is, to find the most appropriate solution in a specific case.

² Discretionary powers can differ from the perspective of the holder, as follows: executive discretionary powers (which are held by public office holders within the executive branch and are exercised by making an executive decision); administrative discretionary powers (which are used by public officials when resolving cases in administrative proceedings and deciding on the rights, obligations and legal interests of citizens) and judicial discretionary powers (which refer to the powers of public prosecutors and courts - most often referring to the right to free judicial decision-making).

³ In the Barel case, when communist candidates were excluded from the competition for admission to the National School of Administrative Affairs on the basis of the discretionary authority of ministers, lawyer Moro Giaferri emphasized in a parliamentary debate that: "discretionary authority is an authority that should be used with discretion (prudence, attention)". This is a political, not a legal formulation. However, in terms of law, certain restrictions, even when it comes to discretionary authority, mean that the freedom of the administration is not complete, but is subordinated to the principle of legality.

case; 3. observes the principle of equality before the law by avoiding unfair discrimination; 4. maintains a proper balance between any adverse effects which its decision may have on the rights, liberties or interests of persons and the purpose which it pursues; 5. takes its decision within a time which is reasonable having regard to the matter at stake and 6. applies any general administrative guidelines in a consistent manner while at the same time taking account of the particular circumstances of each case.

2. THE NECESSITY OF DISCRETIONARY POWERS

The law, by its very nature, cannot predetermine or regulate every conceivable factual situation that may arise in social and legal relations. To assume that the legislator is capable of prescribing exhaustive and rigid norms for all administrative interactions, thereby eliminating any scope for autonomous decision-making, would be a legal fiction. Inevitably, there exists a residual domain of discretion – a sphere of administrative latitude - within which public authorities, guided by the purpose of the law and the principles of proportionality, legality, and reasonableness, must exercise their decisions in light of the specific circumstances of each case.

However, free assessment must not represent arbitrariness, i.e. arbitrariness of the decision-making body. The body cannot act according to its personal will or mood, but is nevertheless bound by the general rules for the performance of its service and function, which must be performed in accordance with the law and the public interest. Decisions made under free assessment must be made within the limits of the authorization and in accordance with the purpose that was to be achieved with such authorization (Davitkovski B. & Pavlovska Daneva A. p. 279).

According to Hicks (2024, p.365-375), the discretionary powers have three faces: the first face of discretion is the power to decide and distribute; the second face of discretion is the power to interpret and enforce and the third face of discretion is the power to disclose and expose.

3. THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL DIMENSIONS OF THE EXERCISE OF DISCRETIONARY POWERS

In legal theory, the analysis of discretionary powers is closely tied to the concept of the rule of law, which requires that public institutions operate strictly in accordance with the principle of legality. This implies that their actions must remain within the boundaries established by law, thereby minimizing the scope for arbitrary decision-making. Excessive latitude could otherwise jeopardize both the principle of legality and the legal certainty guaranteed to citizens.

Legal science conceptualizes discretionary powers as inherent in legal norms contained within abstract and general acts (laws, by-laws), which are subsequently concretized through their application to individual cases and materialized in specific administrative acts (decisions, rulings, or solutions). From the perspective of normative construction, discretionary power is frequently indicated by formulations such as “*may*”, which confer upon the competent authority a legally sanctioned margin of appreciation. Nevertheless, such discretion is not unlimited; it remains bounded by the principles of legality, proportionality, and the prohibition of arbitrariness. Norms granting discretionary powers are embedded throughout the hierarchy of legal acts, thereby reflecting a systematic delegation of evaluative authority to administrative bodies.

Legal theorist Grey (1979, p. 114) emphasizes that the limits of discretionary powers are defined in two cases *Boulis* and *Congreve*. According to him, these limits can

be summarized as a duty to act: (a) in good faith, (b) uninfluenced by irrelevant considerations or motives, (c) reasonably, and (d) within the statutory bounds of the discretion.

The Constitution, as the highest general legal act of the state, does not contain such norms. Laws, as second-level acts, contain norms with discretionary powers. At the third level are the by-laws that elaborate parts of the laws, and they are most often adopted by the state administration bodies or the Government of the Republic of North Macedonia (procedures, rulebooks, decrees, decisions, instructions, programs, solutions and conclusions) that have "erga omnes" legal effect.

With specific acts (decisions), institutions decide on the rights, obligations and legal interests of citizens and refer to legal and natural persons, and they have "inter partes" legal effect.⁴

The most important laws in the Macedonian legal system that directly mention discretionary powers are: the Law on General Administrative Procedure (LAAP), the Law on Administrative Disputes (LAD), the Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest (LPCI) and the Criminal Code (CC).

The Law on General Administrative Procedure in Article 5 paragraph 3 states that "if a public authority is authorized by law to decide on a discretionary basis, the administrative act should be adopted within the limits of the law granting the authorization, in accordance with the purpose for which the authorization was granted and be specifically explained".

The Law on Administrative Disputes as a procedural law only determines how administrative courts act when a case related to discretionary powers is brought before them, and Article 6 paragraph 2 of the Administrative Disputes Act stipulates that "an administrative dispute cannot be conducted regarding the correct application of the free assessment by a public authority (discretionary power) when adopting an individual administrative act, but it can be conducted regarding the legality of such an act and the limits of such power". Additionally, Article 60, paragraph 3, line 1, stipulates that "the court cannot decide on the merits in full jurisdiction if the disputed act was adopted with the discretionary authority of the authorities, but the court shall annul the disputed individual administrative act and return it for re-decision to the authority that adopted it".

The Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest recognizes discretionary powers as one of the greatest risks to corruption, and in Article 8, paragraph 6 of the Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest, the term "risk of corruption" means "inappropriate use of discretionary powers".

The Criminal Code in Article 353-c provides for "a prison sentence of three months to three years if an official or responsible person in a public enterprise or public institution violates the legal regulations on conflict of interest or on conscientious conduct in the exercise of discretionary authority, by failing to exercise due supervision or in any other way clearly acts negligently in the exercise of his or her authority and duties and thereby obtains for himself or another some benefit or causes harm to another".

The remaining laws in the Macedonian legal system confer discretionary powers to public sector institutions, either explicitly or implicitly, through vague and broadly interpreted legal norms. The lack of a consistent administrative practice results in arbitrary decision-

⁴ From a legal perspective, all solutions provided for by the legal norm are of equal value, and the competent authority assesses the solution that best meets the reasons for public interest and expediency in that case.

making by authorities, which undermines both the principle of legality and the legal certainty of citizens. (Discretionary Powers Report, p. 10-11).

In practice, the use of discretionary powers is very widespread, and there is no institution that does not use them. Their use is especially problematic in cases where there is no legal basis for their use, where the institution itself decides on its own discretion to decide on a certain "right" (powers that are not provided for by law), determines the criteria for that "right" on its own discretion, decides on its own discretion who will receive and who will not receive that "right", and determines the scope, i.e. the amount of that "right" if it concerns certain financial resources.

Discretionary powers are not resistant to abuse and, in the absence of a clear procedure and guidelines for their application and control, serve as an instrument for materializing corruption (Final report of the project "Assessment of Vulnerability to Corruption in Employment Policies and Procedures, with a Special Focus on Nepotism, Cronyism and Clientelism", 2021).

Professor Wade (Breban, 2002, p.206) points out that the very essence of discretionary power also means the right to make mistakes, which is also accepted in French law, by introducing the concept of a manifest error of assessment, which means that the holder of discretionary power can make an oversight in the assessment, but does not have the right to make a noticeable error.

The choice of the right measure in discretionary powers⁵ is a very important political-legal issue, because the construction of so-called legal gaps depends on its necessary and necessary representation, and its enormous (excessive) application increases the possibilities for their incorrect application and abuse.

However, the right of discretionary decision-making of the administration for certain administrative areas is represented in all legal systems, including the legal system of the Republic of North Macedonia, and the possibilities for its abuse should be reduced (Davitkovski B. & Pavlovska Daneva A. p.279).

Discretionary administrative acts or acts adopted at discretion are those acts whose author is authorized, at discretion, to determine whether in a specific case he will adopt an act at all and, if he does, what the content of the act will be. Discretionary acts contain the authority for the administration to choose between two or more legally equal alternatives.

4. MECHANISMS TO PREVENT ABUSE OF DISCRETIONARY POWERS BY INSTITUTIONS

According to the established institutional system, the acts of the public administration are subject to supervision and control by the higher authorities (ministries), specialized bodies (second-instance commissions) or the courts (Administrative, Higher Administrative and Constitutional Court).

Supervision is exercised over the legality of general acts (rulebooks, statutes, etc.), over specific acts, over the operation and over the material and financial operations of the administration and is carried out by independent institutions such as the Parliament of the Republic of Macedonia, the State Audit Office (SAO), the Ombudsman (OP), the State

⁵ When it comes to discretionary acts, i.e. discretionary decisions, there are certain guidelines and rules according to which the administration must be guided in decision-making: the discretionary authority must be provided for by law; the act must be adopted in a legally prescribed procedure; the form of the act must be respected; the authority must not be exceeded; the authority should not be used contrary to the purpose for which it was granted.

Commission for the Prevention of Corruption (SCPC) and others, whose recommendations have only a consultative role and do not carry legal consequences for the institutions. This is important, because the abuse of discretionary powers can only be determined when their acts are effectively controlled.

With regard to specific acts of the administration, i.e. decisions by which it decides in administrative procedures where it has discretionary powers (discretionary decisions), citizens can:

- file a regular legal remedy, an appeal before the State Commission for Decision-Making in Administrative Procedures and Employment Procedures in the Second Instance and

- if they are not satisfied with the second instance decision, they can initiate an administrative dispute by filing an appeal with the Administrative Court, and further use extraordinary legal remedies with the Higher Administrative Court.

The laws with the vague and poorly defined provisions of the laws and bylaws grant the institutions tacit freedom in certain situations to act as they deem best. This combination of shortcomings in the system provides greater scope for the abuse of discretionary powers violating the principle of legality in the work of the public administration, the legal certainty of citizens and making the rule of law impossible.

Silveira and Ettner (2020) in their paper propose several mechanisms (legislative drafting tools) for limiting discretionary powers: a) clear identification of discretionary powers; b) avoid using discretion as a principle; c) avoid vague legal concepts; d) use discretion when necessary; and e) when possible use non-exhaustive lists of cases.

5. DISCRETIONARY POWERS IN THE JURISPRUDENCE OF THE ECtHR

The ECtHR has addressed the question of discretionary powers in a number of cases. This paper examines several judgments that, either explicitly or implicitly, reveal instances where national authorities abused their discretionary powers, resulting in violations of the ECHR.

The Court consistently holds that broad discretionary powers are not per se incompatible with the Convention - but they must be:

- prescribed by law (clear, accessible, foreseeable) (*Gillan and Quinton v. United Kingdom*, Application no. 4158/05), paras. 76, 77),
- circumscribed by safeguards against arbitrariness (*Case of Kruslin v. France*, Application No. 11801/85),
- be necessary in a democratic society (*Roman Zakharov v. Russia*, Application no. 47143/06), and
- proportionate to the legitimate aim pursued (*ML v. North Macedonia*, Application no. 30206/23, para 56).

Where safeguards are absent, or where discretion is exercised arbitrarily, the Court finds violations.

The case of *Gillan and Quinton v. United Kingdom* (para.87) concerns stop-and-search measures under Terrorism Act 2000 that give powers to police to stop people without reasonable suspicion. In conclusion, the Court considers that:

“the powers of authorization and confirmation as well as those of stop and search under sections 44 and 45 of the 2000 Act are neither sufficiently circumscribed nor subject to adequate legal safeguards against abuse. They are not, therefore, “in accordance with the law” and it follows that there has been a violation of Article 8 of the Convention”.

According to ECtHR, the absence of any requirement of “reasonable suspicion” gave the police “an almost unfettered discretion”. So, the Court found violation of Article 8.

1. In the case of *Kruslin v. France* the applicant’s telephone was tapped in the context of a criminal investigation. French law at the time allowed wiretapping but gave very little guidance on **who could authorize it, for how long, or under what conditions**. The Court’s reasoning reads as follows:

“Above all, the system does not for the time being afford adequate safeguards against various possible abuses. For example, the categories of people liable to have their telephones tapped by judicial order and the nature of the offences which may give rise to such an order are nowhere defined. Nothing obliges a judge to set a limit on the duration of telephone tapping. Similarly unspecified are the procedure for drawing up the summary reports containing intercepted conversations; the precautions to be taken in order to communicate the recordings intact and in their entirety for possible inspection by the judge (who can hardly verify the number and length of the original tapes on the spot) and by the defense; and the circumstances in which recordings may or must be erased or the tapes be destroyed, in particular where an accused has been discharged by an investigating judge or acquitted by a court. The information provided by the Government on these various points shows at best the existence of a practice, but a practice lacking the necessary regulatory control in the absence of legislation or case-law (para. 35)”

So, ECtHR found that the French law did not indicate with sufficient clarity regarding the **scope** of the authorities’ discretion, and the **minimum safeguards** required to prevent abuse. The lack of clear rules meant that the discretion was **not circumscribed by safeguards against arbitrariness**. The Court found violation of Article 8. In the case *Roman Zakharov v. Russia* the Court found violation of Article 8 because Russian law allowed interception of communications with broad discretion and minimal oversight and it lacked adequate safeguards. ECtHR states as follows:

“In view of the shortcomings identified above, the Court finds that Russian law does not meet the “quality of law” requirement and is incapable of keeping the “interference” to what is “necessary in a democratic society”. There has accordingly been a violation of Article 8 of the Convention (paras. 304, 305)”

The case *ML v. North Macedonia* concerns domestic barring order (restrictions on proximity to family members), so the Court examined proportionality and safeguards in the order:

“Lastly, the applicant was not even informed, let alone involved in any such reassessment conducted by the pre-trial judge, and the Government did not argue otherwise. His subsequent request of 25 July 2023 that the barring order be lifted apparently went unanswered. The Court cannot but conclude that, in respect of the mandatory reassessment of whether the need for the barring order persisted, the applicant was not afforded any procedural guarantees capable of enabling him to protect his interest in being reunited with his daughter.

In sum, the insufficient reasoning of the three-judge panel confirming the barring order, together with the absence of formal reasoned decisions, the lack of meaningful scrutiny on the basis of relevant updated information and the failure to involve the applicant in the mandatory periodic reassessment of the barring order, fell short of the procedural requirements under Article 8 of the Convention (paras. 78,79)”.

The Court concludes that there has been a violation of Article 8 of the Convention.

The case of *Grzęda v. Poland* concerns the premature termination of the applicant's term of office as a judicial member of the National Council of the Judiciary (Krajowa Rada Sądownictwa, KRS) in Poland due to legislative reforms of 2017. The applicant, Judge Jan Grzęda, claimed that the termination of his term of office without the possibility of judicial protection violated his rights under Article 6 § 1 of the European Convention on Human Rights (the right to a fair trial, including access to a court). The ECtHR, in a landmark judgment of 15 March 2022, found a violation of Article 6(1), emphasizing the crucial importance of judicial independence and the need for procedural safeguards against arbitrary interference with judicial functions. According to the Court, the reform granted broad discretionary powers to the Polish legislative and executive authorities to restructure the judiciary, including the termination of judicial mandates without transparent criteria or accountability. The ECtHR criticized this as a threat to judicial independence, as it allowed for unchecked political interference in judicial functions. The absence of judicial protection increased the risk of arbitrary exercise of discretionary powers, a key concern in the context of legal imperfections.

Grzęda v. Poland is a landmark case in the ECtHR's case law on judicial independence. It reinforces the principle that judges must have access to a court to challenge decisions affecting their status, particularly in the context of legislative or executive interference. The judgment has significant implications for Poland's judicial system, calling for reforms to comply with Article 6(1). It also adds to international pressure on Poland to address concerns about the rule of law, as reflected in related EU proceedings and Council of Europe reports.

The case sets a standard for all Council of Europe member states, underlining the need for procedural safeguards to protect judicial independence and prevent arbitrary exercise of power. It is particularly relevant for countries undergoing judicial reform or facing problems with political influence over the judiciary.

While the case is specific to Poland, its principles are relevant to any jurisdiction, including North Macedonia, where concerns exist about judicial independence, legal gaps and corruption. For example, reports by the State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption (SCPC) have identified legal gaps and excessive discretionary powers in areas such as urban planning and local government (Annual Report on the Work of the State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption for 2023, p. 63).

In case *Baka v. Hungary*, former President of the Supreme Court of Hungary, was prematurely removed from office in 2011 due to constitutional and legislative changes, partly in response to his criticism of judicial reforms. He was not able to challenge the decision in court. The ECtHR found a violation of Article 6(1) (right of access to a court) and Article 10 (freedom of expression), finding that the removal was retaliation for his criticism and that the legislative changes undermined judicial independence. ECtHR states (Information Note on the Court's case-law no. 174, 2014, p. 3):

“As regards the proportionality of the interference, the applicant’s term of office as President of the Supreme Court had been terminated three and a half years before the end of the fixed term applicable under the legislation in force at the time of his election. Furthermore, although the applicant had remained in office as a judge of the new Kúria, the premature termination of his mandate had had pecuniary consequences”.

Accordingly, the ECtHR implicitly found that the legislation granted the authorities broad powers to remove Baka without transparent criteria.

In the *Case of Ramos Nunes De Carvalho E Sá v. Portugal* ECtHR also found a violation of Article 6(1) of the ECHR on account of the lack of impartial and independent judicial review of disciplinary sanctions, highlighting systemic problems in the Portuguese disciplinary system. In this case the applicant, a judge in Portugal, was subject to disciplinary proceedings by the High Council of the Judiciary for alleged professional misconduct. She alleged that the proceedings were unfair, with limited access to judicial review and bias in the judicial decision-making. From the perspective of discretionary powers, practically the Supreme Court had considerable discretionary powers, which gave rise to a risk of bias. ECtHR concluded that:

“In the light of the foregoing the Court concludes that, in the circumstances of the present case – taking into consideration the specific context of disciplinary proceedings conducted against a judge, the seriousness of the penalties, the fact that the procedural guarantees before the CSM were limited, and the need to assess factual evidence going to the applicant’s credibility and that of the witnesses and constituting a decisive aspect of the case – the combined effect of two factors, namely the insufficiency of the judicial review performed by the Judicial Division of the Supreme Court and the lack of a hearing either at the stage of the disciplinary proceedings or at the judicial review stage, meant that the applicant’s case was not heard in accordance with the requirements of Article 6 § 1 of the Convention (para.214)”.

CONCLUSION

Discretionary powers represent a vital component of modern legal systems, as they provide the necessary flexibility for institutions to act in situations where rigid adherence to legal norms cannot adequately address the particularities of a case. Yet, this very freedom of decision-making carries the inherent risk of unequal, arbitrary, or even abusive use.

The central challenge, therefore, lies in striking a balance between the need for discretion and the imperative of legal certainty and the protection of civil rights. Legislators must set clear boundaries and criteria for the exercise of such powers, while judicial oversight and adherence to the principles of the rule of law serve as essential safeguards against arbitrary practices.

In this light, discretionary powers should not be regarded as unlimited authority, but rather as a tool which – when exercised in line with the principles of fairness, equality, and proportionality – can enhance both the efficiency and the justice of legal application.

The principles of ECtHR cases shown above offer a roadmap for addressing systemic challenges in the legal system of North Macedonia, as well. By applying these principles, the country can strengthen judicial independence, close legal gaps, regulate

discretionary powers, improve judicial discretion, and strengthen the fight against corruption. Reforms based on these standards will not only bring Macedonian legislation into line with the European Convention, but will also increase public trust in the judiciary and the rule of law.

REFERENCES

- Annual Report on the Work of the State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption* (2023).
- Breban, G. (2002). *Administrativno pravo Francuske*, JP Službeni list SRJ Beograd, CID, Podgorica.
- Criminal Code, Official Gazette of RM, no. 37/96.
- Davitkovski B. Pavlovska Daneva A. *Administrative Law – first part (material law)*. University St. Kiril and Metodij, Skopje.
- Discretionary Powers Report* (2024). State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption.
- Grey, J. H. *Discretion in Administrative Law*. (1979). Osgoode Hall Law Journal, 17.1.
- Guidelines for the exercise of discretionary powers* (2021). State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption.
- Hicks D. (2024). *Argumentation and Discretionary Power*, Proceedings of the Tenth Conference of the International Society for the Study of Argumentation, University of Leiden, The Netherlands.
- Information Note on the Court's case-law No. 174, May 2014, p.3.
- Final report of the project "Assessment of Vulnerability to Corruption in Employment Policies and Procedures, with a Special Focus on Nepotism, Cronyism and Clientelism"*. (2020). State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption.
- Law on General Administrative Procedure, Official Gazette of RM, no. 124/15, 65/18.
- Law on Administrative Disputes, Official Gazette of RNM, no. 96/19.
- Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest, Official Gazette of RM, no. 12/19.
- Munir, B., Khan, A. N., & Ahmad, N. (2020). *Necessity of Discretionary Powers: A Critical Appreciation as a Necessary Evil*, Global Regional Review, V (III).
- Recommendation No. R (80) 2 of The Committee Of Ministers Concerning The Exercise of Discretionary Powers by Administrative Authorities* (Adopted By The Committee Of Ministers On 11 March 1980 at The 316th Meeting Of The Ministers' Deputies).
- Tiago Silveira J. & Ettner D. (2020). *Legislative drafting tools preventing arbitrariness in discretionary powers*, The Theory and Practice in Legislation, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Gillan and Quinton v. United Kingdom (Application no. 4158/05).
- Case of Kruslin v. France (Application No. 11801/85).
- Roman Zakharov v. Russia (Application no. 47143/06).
- ML v. North Macedonia, (Application no. 30206/23).
- Grzęda v. Poland, (Application no. 43572/18).
- Baka v. Hungary (Application no. 20261/12).
- Ramos Nunes De Carvalho E Sá v. Portugal (Applications nos. 55391/13, 57728/13 and 74041/13).